

Synthesis and antibacterial activity of 2- $\{[3\text{-phenyl-7-substituted-2-(phenylimino)-2,3\text{-dihydro}[1,3]\text{thiazolo}[4,5-d]\text{pyrimidin-5-yl}]\text{imino}\}$ -3-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one

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Abstract : In the present investigation, desired fused ring system 2- $\{[3\text{-phenyl-7-substituted-2-(phenylimino)-2,3\text{-dihydro}[1,3]\text{thiazolo}[4,5-d]\text{pyrimidin-5-yl}]\text{imino}\}$ -3-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (1a-c) have been described. *N,N'*-Diphenylthiourea is converted to 3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (1a-c), the reaction with chloroacetic acid and sodium acetate in acetic acid. This on Claisen condensation with various aromatic aldehydes gave corresponding 5-arylidene derivatives (2a-e). These are treated with guanidine nitrate to furnish 2-aminopyrimidine derivatives (3a-e). These when reacted with ammonium thiocyanate in dilute HCl, 1-[3-phenyl-7-substituted-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]thiourea (4a-e) are yielded. These compounds are converted to corresponding thiazolidinone derivatives (5a-e) by cyclisation with chloroacetic acid and sodium acetate. Subsequent condensation of 5a-c with bromoethoxyphthalimide gave the title compounds 6a-c. The structures of synthesized compounds have been confirmed by spectral and analytical studies. Six compounds have been studied for antibacterial activity which show moderate to weaker activity.

Keywords : *N,N'*-Diphenylthiourea, chloroacetic acid, pyrimidine, thiazolidinone, bromoethoxyphthalimide.

Introduction

Thiazolidin-4-one scaffold is a powerful biophore fragment used in the rational design of drug like compounds as innovative drug prototypes. The chemistry of thiazolidinone ring system is of considerable interest as it is a core structure in various synthetic pharmaceuticals and played an important role in medicinal chemistry¹. Moreover these have been studied extensively because of their easy accessibility, diverse chemical reactivity and broad spectrum biological activity such as anti-diarrheal², anticonvulsant³, antimicrobial⁴, antibacterial⁵, antifungal⁶, anti-diabetic⁷, antihistaminic⁸, anticancer⁹, anti-HIV¹⁰, anti-tuberculosis¹¹, anti-cardiac¹², anti-ischemic¹³, analgesic¹⁴, Ca²⁺ channel blockers¹⁵, PAF antagonist, cardioprotective¹⁶, cyclooxygenase inhibitory¹⁷, antiplatelet activating factor¹⁸, nonpeptide thrombin receptor antagonist¹⁹, and tumor necrosis factor- α antagonist²⁰. According to Andres 4-thiazolidinone may be considered as phosphate bioisosteres and therefore inhibit the bacterial enzyme MurB which is involved in the biosynthesis of pep-

tidoglycan layers of the cell wall²¹. Current research in the area of pharmacological potential of 1,3-thiazolidin-4-one derivatives, a well known group of biologically active compounds allowed us to identify the anticancer activity of some derivatives that possessed low acute toxicity and cytotoxicity²². A de novo structure based design has demonstrated that the 4-thiazolidinones inhibit an enzyme RmulC, which is an essential component for the biosynthesis of dTDP-rhamnose²³.

Condensed pyrimidine derivatives possessing anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity is well documented in literature^{24,25}. Apart from anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity these molecules also exhibit a wide variety of other biological activity viz. fungicidal²⁶, antiviral²⁷, anti-HIV²⁸, antihypertensive²⁹, for treatment of neurological and psychiatric disorders³⁰ and hyper uricemia³¹. Especially thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidines are patented as arteriosclerosis³², immunomodulator³³, antirheumatic³⁴, antidepressant³⁵, cardioprotective³⁶, antihypertensive³⁷ and antimicrobial³⁸ agents. Therefore, it was thought of interest to

construct a system, which may combine these biolabile rings together in a single molecular framework to see the additive effect towards their biological activities.

Results and discussion

The required 3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**1**) was prepared by the condensation of *N,N*-diphenylthiourea with chloroacetic acid in glacial acetic acid containing anhydrous sodium acetate. IR spectrum displayed a definite absorption at 1720 cm^{-1} due to imide carbonyl group. The structure was further supported by ^1H NMR spectrum exhibiting signal at δ 4.30 (CO-CH₂-S). When compound **1** was condensed with aromatic aldehydes in acetic acid and sodium acetate gave corresponding arylidene derivatives (**2a-e**). ^1H NMR spectrum of these compounds were devoid of a singlet at δ 4.30 exhibited by their precursors and appearance of singlet at δ 6.30 for C=CH-Ar. This clearly supports that the condensation took place between compound **1** and aromatic aldehydes. Cyclocondensation of **2a-e** with guanidine nitrate in ethanol yielded 3-phenyl-7-substituted-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-*d*]pyrimidin-5-amine (**3a-e**). The intense band at 3350 and 3420 cm^{-1} for the NH₂ group attached to the pyrimidine ring and ^1H NMR signal at δ 6.85 (singlet) confirm the structure of these compounds. Compounds **3a-e** were treated with ammonium thiocyanate in dilute HCl to afford corresponding thiourea derivatives (**4a-e**). Structure of these compounds was confirmed by ^1H NMR signal at δ 8.63 (multiplet) for 3H of thiourea moiety. Cyclocondensation of **4a-e** to 2-[(2z)-3-phenyl-7-substituted-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-*d*]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino}-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**5a-e**) were carried out by the reaction of chloroacetic acid in ethanol under reflux for 8–10 h. Formation of the compounds was confirmed by absorption at 1758 cm^{-1} due to C=O group and also ^1H NMR signal at δ 8.2 (NH of thiazolidinone ring) and 4.35 (COCH₂S). Base catalysed condensation of **5a-e** with bromoethoxyphthalimide in acetone yielded 2-[[3-phenyl-7-substituted-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-*d*]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-3-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**6a-e**). Absence of singlet for the proton of NH and appearance of two triplets at δ 4.67 and 3.72 (for OCH₂ and NCH₂ groups) corresponding to their phthalimidoxy group in the ^1H NMR spectrum confirm

the structure of **6a**. Moreover, the mass spectrum of **6a** gave peak at m/z 683, which corresponds to the molecular weight of C₃₆H₂₅N₇O₄S₂ of the assigned structure.

Experimental

General procedures : Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are therefore uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel G TLC plates of 2 mm thickness using *n*-hexane and ethyl acetate as solvent system. The visualization of spots was carried out in an iodine chamber. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded in the $4000\text{--}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ranges using KBr discs on FTIR IR RX1 Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometers and ^1H NMR were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 MHz spectrometer (CDCl₃) using TMS as an internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol AccuTOF JMS-T100LC Mass spectrometer. Bromoethoxyphthalimide was prepared by reported method³⁹.

Synthesis of 3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (1) : A mixture of *N,N*-diphenylthiourea (2.28 g, 0.01 mol), sodium acetate (1.64 g, 0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (16 mL) and chloroacetic acid (0.94 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed for 5 h. After completion of the reaction, cold water was added in the reaction mixture. White colored product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3120 (C-H str., ArH), 1720 (C=O str.), 1580 (C=N str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 7.74–7.20 (10H, m, ArH), 4.30 (2H, s, CH₂); MS : m/z : 268 [M]⁺.

Synthesis of 3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-5-(phenylmethylidene)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (2a) : To a refluxing mixture of **1** (2.68 g, 0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (1.64 g, 0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 mL), benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 0.01 mol) added and refluxing was continued for 16 h. After completion of reaction, ice cold water was added to the cold reaction mixture. Solid obtained was filtered, washed and crystallized from ethanol.

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3090 (C-H str., ArH), 1734 (C=O str.), 1590 (C=N str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 7.48–7.17 (15H, m, ArH), 6.10 (1H, s, C=CHAr); MS : m/z : 356 [M]⁺.

Similarly, compounds **2b-e** were prepared with some change in reflux time and reaction workup. Their physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data for synthesized compounds

Compd.	Mol. formula	Mol. weight	R	Yield (%)	M.p. °C	N (%)	
						Found	(Calcd.)
1	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	268.33	-	58	148	10.05	(10.44)
2a	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	356.44	C ₆ H ₅	65	128	7.10	(7.86)
2b	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	386.46	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60	136	7.42	(7.25)
2c	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ OS	390.88	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	70	147	6.20	(7.17)
2d	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ OS	399.50	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	72	160	10.00	(10.52)
2e	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	401.43	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	76	100	10.59	(10.47)
3a	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	395.47	C ₆ H ₅	74	90	17.00	(17.17)
3b	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	425.50	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	75	96	16.10	(16.46)
3c	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S	429.92	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	80	105	16.44	(16.29)
3d	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₆ S	438.54	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	60	114	18.40	(19.16)
3e	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S	440.47	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	67	139	19.22	(19.08)
4a	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₆ S ₂	454.56	C ₆ H ₅	85	120	18.03	(18.49)
4b	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₆ OS ₂	484.59	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	80	144	16.78	(17.34)
4c	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ClN ₆ S	489.01	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	76	154	17.33	(17.19)
4d	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₇ S ₂	497.63	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	72	132	19.28	(19.70)
4e	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂ S ₂	499.56	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	61	169	19.10	(19.63)
5a	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₆ OS ₂	494.59	C ₆ H ₅	56	135	16.36	(16.99)
5b	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	524.61	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	54	100	16.20	(16.02)
5c	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ ClN ₆ OS ₂	529.03	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	51	116	15.35	(15.89)
5d	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₇ OS ₂	537.65	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	58	172	18.48	(18.24)
5e	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₃ S ₂	539.58	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	62	121	17.69	(18.17)
6a	C ₃₆ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₄ S ₂	683.75	C ₆ H ₅	57	80	13.88	(14.34)
6b	C ₃₇ H ₂₇ N ₇ O ₅ S ₂	713.78	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	64	50	13.30	(13.74)
6c	C ₃₆ H ₂₄ ClN ₇ O ₄ S ₂	718.20	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	52	140	13.21	(13.65)
6d	C ₃₈ H ₃₀ N ₈ O ₄ S ₂	726.82	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	57	110	15.08	(15.42)
6e	C ₃₆ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₆ S ₂	728.75	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	65	90	15.44	(15.38)

Table 2. Results of antibacterial activity of synthesized compounds

Compd.	Zone of inhibition of growth in mm (activity index)			
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
5c	7 (0.46)	10 (0.63)	9 (0.50)	5 (0.29)
6a	8 (0.53)	11 (0.69)	11 (0.61)	7 (0.41)
6b	8 (0.53)	12 (0.75)	12 (0.67)	8 (0.47)
6c	10 (0.67)	13 (0.81)	13 (0.72)	10 (0.59)
6d	9 (0.60)	12 (0.75)	10 (0.56)	9 (0.53)
6e	10 (0.67)	13 (0.81)	11 (0.61)	9 (0.53)
Standard	15	16	18	17

5-[[4-Chlorophenyl)methylidene]-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (2b) : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3060 (C-H str., ArH), 1705 (C=O str.), 1535 (C=N str.), 1080 (C-O str.), 2940 (CH₃ str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 7.68-7.37 (14H, m, ArH), 6.22 (1H, s, C=CHAR), 3.60

(3H, s, OCH₃); MS : m/z : 386 [M]⁺, 388 [M+2]⁺.

5-[[4-Methoxyphenyl)methylidene]-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (2c) : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3088 (C-H str., ArH), 1745 (C=O str.), 1554 (C=N str.), 748 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 7.8-7.41 (14H, m, ArH), 6.24 (1H, s, C=CHAR); MS : m/z : 390 [M]⁺.

5-[[4-N,N-Dimethylaminophenyl)methylidene]-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (2d) : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3110 (C-H str., ArH), 1715 (C=O str.), 1550 (C=N str.), 2950 (CH₃ str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 7.84-7.62 (14H, m, ArH), 6.30 (1H, s, C=CHAR), 2.84 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂); MS : m/z : 399 [M]⁺.

5-[[3-Nitrophenyl)methylidene]-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (2e) : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3130

Reaction Scheme

(C-H str., ArH), 1738 (C=O str.), 1545 (C=N str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 7.42-7.03 (14H, m, ArH), 6.26 (1H, s, C=CHAR); MS : m/z : 401 [M]⁺.

Synthesis of 3,7-diphenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-amine (3a) : Compound 2a (3.56 g, 0.01 mol) and guanidine nitrate (1.22

g, 0.01 mol) were dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 mL) and refluxed for 1 h. 10% NaOH solution was added to the reaction mixture and refluxing continued for 8 h, then the reaction mixture was cooled and poured on crushed ice to get a white colored product, **3a**, which was purified by recrystallization from ethanol.

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3050 (C-H str., ArH), 1563 (C=N str.), 3350, 3420 (NH str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.71–7.44 (15H, m, ArH), 6.22 (2H, s, NH_2); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 127.07, 127.28, 127.62, 128.15, 128.62, 128.77, 128.98, 129.25, 129.58, 129.92, 130.23, 130.80, 145.70, 148.62, 159.28, 160.73; MS : m/z : 395 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$.

The other substrates **3b-e** were synthesized by little modification in reflux time. Their physical and analytical data are reported in Table 1.

7-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-amine (3b) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3130 (C-H str., ArH), 1590 (C=N str.), 3356, 3470 (NH str.), 1085 (C-O str.), 2910 (CH_3 str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.48–7.29 (14H, m, ArH), 6.87 (2H, s, NH_2), 3.66 (3H, s, OCH_3); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 127.69, 127.82, 128.16, 128.48, 129.28, 129.45, 129.50, 130.64, 130.84, 130.92, 131.81, 132.39, 133.56, 145.60, 149.23, 159.43, 160.24; MS : m/z : 425 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, 427 $[\text{M}+2]^{+\bullet}$.

7-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-amine (3c) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3108 (C-H str., ArH), 1520 (C=N str.), 3370, 3450 (NH str.), 768 (C-Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.52–7.14 (14H, m, ArH), 6.89 (2H, s, NH_2); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 29.58, 127.28, 127.80, 128.38, 128.72, 129.09, 129.66, 129.92, 130.14, 130.45, 130.63, 131.28, 131.59, 132.43, 145.35, 149.89, 159.53, 160.54; MS : m/z : 429 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$.

7-(4-N,N-Dimethylaminophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-amine (3d) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3095 (C-H str., ArH), 1508 (C=N str.), 3335, 3465 (NH str.), 2965 (CH_3 str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.84–7.44 (14H, m, ArH), 6.90 (2H, s, NH_2), 2.87 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 30.32, 127.48, 127.79, 128.24, 128.56, 129.18, 129.53, 129.89, 130.24, 130.68, 130.82, 131.18, 131.95, 145.05, 149.12, 159.26, 160.73; MS : m/z : 438 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$.

7-(3-Nitrophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-

dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-amine (3e) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3054 (C-H str., ArH), 1565 (C=N str.), 3352, 3470 (NH str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.75–7.54 (14H, m, ArH), 6.65 (2H, s, NH_2); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 127.06, 127.28, 128.52, 128.75, 129.33, 129.59, 130.28, 130.63, 130.81, 131.22, 131.79, 135.52, 145.40, 148.56, 159.16, 160.65; MS : m/z : 440 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$.

Synthesis of 1-[3,7-diphenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]thiourea (4a) : To compound **3a** (3.95 g, 0.01 mol), hydrochloric acid (100 mL, 1 N) was added till the solution becomes clear. Then ammonium thiocyanate (1.52 g, 0.02 mol) was added to it. Reaction mixture was refluxed for 8 h. Solid separated on cooling was filtered and dried. It was recrystallized from rectified spirit.

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3057 (C-H str., ArH), 1583 (C=N str.), 3340, 3462 (NH str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.72–7.48 (15H, m, ArH), 8.22 (3H, m, NH.C=S.NH_2); MS : m/z : 454 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$.

Other compounds **4b-e** were also synthesized by following same procedure with minor change in reflux time. Their physical and analytical data are mentioned in Table 1.

1-[7-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]thiourea (4b) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3146 (C-H str., ArH), 1510 (C=N str.), 3320, 3485 (NH str.), 1064 (C-O str.), 2958 (CH_3 str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.46–7.21 (14H, m, ArH), 8.50 (3H, m, NH.C=S.NH_2), 3.62 (3H, s, OCH_3); MS : m/z : 484 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, 486 $[\text{M}+2]^{+\bullet}$.

1-[7-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]thiourea (4c) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3078 (C-H str., ArH), 1525 (C=N str.), 330, 3452 (NH str.), 787 (C-Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.85–7.23 (14H, m, ArH), 8.62 (3H, m, NH.C=S.NH_2); MS : m/z : 490 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$.

1-[7-(4-N,N-Dimethylaminophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]thiourea (4d) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3074 (C-H str., ArH), 1575 (C=N str.), 3342, 3455 (NH str.), 2925 (CH_3 str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.47–7.22 (14H, m, ArH), 8.44 (3H, m, NH.C=S.NH_2), 2.89 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$); MS : m/z : 497 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$.

1-[7-(3-Nitrophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-

dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]thiourea (4e) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3059 (C–H str., ArH), 1563 (C=N str.), 3360, 3466 (NH str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.52–7.08 (14H, m, ArH), 8.28 (3H, m, NH.C=S.NH₂); MS : m/z : 499 [M]⁺.

Synthesis of 2-[[3,7-diphenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (5a) : To a suspension of **4a** (4.54 g, 0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 mL), chloroacetic acid (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (1.64 g, 0.02 mol) were added. The reaction mixture was heated for 7 h on steam bath. Reaction mixture was cooled and then poured slowly into ice cold water with constant stirring. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol.

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3079 (C–H str., ArH), 1546 (C=N str.), 3444 (NH str.), 1758 (C=O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.75–7.40 (15H, m, ArH), 8.63 (1H, s, NH), 4.49 (2H, s, SCH₂); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 33.72, 127.23, 127.52, 127.79, 128.46, 128.70, 128.94, 129.24, 129.56, 129.89, 130.16, 130.48, 130.85, 131.29, 145.78, 149.27, 159.34, 160.18, 160.84, 171.30; MS : m/z : 494 [M]⁺.

Likewise, compounds **5b–e** were prepared with some change in reaction conditions. Their characteristic physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

2-[[7-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (5b) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3047 (C–H str., ArH), 1588 (C=N str.), 3450 (NH str.), 1765 (C=O str.), 1060 (C–O str.), 2940 (CH₃ str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.92–7.70 (14H, m, ArH), 8.69 (1H, s, NH), 4.40 (2H, s, SCH₂), 3.64 (3H, s, OCH₃); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 33.35, 127.43, 127.92, 128.24, 128.65, 129.44, 129.57, 129.76, 130.28, 130.42, 130.63, 131.92, 132.56, 133.16, 145.26, 149.35, 159.16, 160.53, 160.79, 171.64; MS : m/z : 524 [M]⁺, 526 [M+2]⁺.

2-[[7-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (5c) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3124 (C–H str., ArH), 1528 (C=N str.), 3410 (NH str.), 1760 (C=O str.), 740 (C–Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.54–7.21 (14H, m, ArH), 8.59 (1H, s, NH), 4.48 (2H, s, SCH₂); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 29.64, 33.48, 127.54, 127.80, 128.69, 128.86, 129.40, 129.55, 129.94, 130.20, 130.63,

130.76, 131.25, 131.87, 132.57, 145.50, 149.69, 159.45, 160.48, 160.72, 171.83; MS : m/z : 530 [M]⁺.

2-[[7-(4-N,N-Dimethylaminophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (5d) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3118 (C–H str., ArH), 1566 (C=N str.), 3480 (NH str.), 2942 (CH₃ str.), 1742 (C=O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.57–7.32 (14H, m, ArH), 8.68 (1H, s, NH), 4.43 (2H, s, SCH₂), 2.83 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 30.28, 33.77, 127.42, 127.64, 128.40, 128.73, 129.24, 129.36, 129.58, 130.22, 130.40, 130.70, 130.99, 131.16, 131.97, 145.59, 149.23, 159.33, 160.40, 160.73, 171.18; MS : m/z : 537 [M]⁺.

2-[[7-(3-Nitrophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (5e) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3074 (C–H str., ArH), 1541 (C=N str.), 3453 (NH str.), 1750 (C=O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.70–7.43 (14H, m, ArH), 8.67 (1H, s, NH), 4.43 (2H, s, SCH₂); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 33.92, 127.29, 127.42, 128.57, 128.88, 129.45, 129.74, 130.30, 130.55, 130.73, 131.27, 131.93, 132.54, 135.29, 145.64, 149.34, 159.75, 160.38, 160.78, 171.48; MS : m/z : 539 [M]⁺.

Synthesis of 2-[[3,7-diphenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino}-3-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (6a) : A mixture of compound **5a** (4.94 g, 0.01 mol) and bromoethoxyphthalimide (2.70 g, 0.01 mol) were dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 mL), pyridine (0.80 mL, 0.01 mol) was added to this reaction mixture as a base. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 18 h. After cooling, the mixture was concentrated to one third by removing the solvent under reduced pressure. The separated solid was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3056 (C–H str., ArH), 1542 (C=N str.), 1734 (C=O str.), 1340 (N–O str.), 1065 (C–O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 7.89–7.47 (19H, m, ArH), 3.72 (2H, t, NCH₂), 4.67 (2H, t, OCH₂), 4.44 (2H, s, SCH₂); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ : 33.48, 34.16, 36.87, 127.40, 127.46, 127.72, 127.87, 128.07, 128.27, 128.69, 129.23, 129.43, 129.88, 130.26, 130.48, 130.89, 131.58, 132.82, 145.52, 149.78, 159.23, 160.43, 160.78, 168.42, 171.80; MS : m/z : 683 [M]⁺.

Compounds **6b–e** were synthesized with some modifi-

cations in reaction conditions. Their physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

2-[[7-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-3-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**6b**) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3128 (C-H str., ArH), 1590 (C=N str.), 1787 (C=O str.), 1355 (N-O str.), 1086 (C-O str.), 2918 (CH_3 str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 7.65-7.27 (18H, m, ArH), 3.78 (2H, t, NCH_2), 4.69 (2H, t, OCH_2), 4.42 (2H, s, SCH_2), 3.61 (3H, s, OCH_3); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 33.42, 34.53, 36.46, 127.15, 127.46, 127.67, 128.17, 128.93, 129.12, 129.34, 129.62, 130.36, 130.52, 130.90, 131.51, 132.46, 132.83, 133.44, 145.13, 149.45, 159.64, 160.10, 160.46, 168.73, 171.62; MS : m/z : 713 $[\text{M}]^+$, 713 $[\text{M}+2]^+$.

2-[[7-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-3-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**6c**) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3134 (C-H str., ArH), 1575 (C=N str.), 1712 (C=O str.), 1372 (N-O str.), 1092 (C-O str.), 756 (C-Cl str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 7.95-7.42 (18H, m, ArH), 3.74 (2H, t, NCH_2), 4.62 (2H, t, OCH_2), 4.46 (2H, s, SCH_2); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 29.83, 33.65, 34.13, 36.44, 127.18, 127.26, 127.64, 128.48, 128.90, 129.15, 129.70, 129.82, 130.24, 130.37, 130.94, 131.45, 131.73, 132.81, 132.94, 145.76, 149.50, 159.67, 160.35, 160.62, 168.59, 171.45; MS : m/z : 719 $[\text{M}]^+$.

2-[[7-(4-N,N-Dimethylaminophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-3-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**6d**) : IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3108 (C-H str., ArH), 1540 (C=N str.), 1766 (C=O str.), 1380 (N-O str.), 1055 (C-O str.), 2946 (CH_3 str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 7.79-7.20 (18H, m, ArH), 3.70 (2H, t, NCH_2), 4.63 (2H, t, OCH_2), 4.40 (2H, s, SCH_2), 2.88 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 30.86, 33.76, 34.46, 36.51, 127.27, 127.54, 127.83, 128.49, 128.56, 129.13, 129.44, 129.66, 130.14, 130.53, 130.73, 130.92, 131.22, 131.68, 132.45, 145.48, 149.93, 159.54, 160.46, 160.72, 168.38, 171.63; MS : m/z : 726 $[\text{M}]^+$.

2-[[7-(3-Nitrophenyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylimino)-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-d]pyrimidin-5-yl]imino]-3-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one (**6e**) : IR (KBr)

cm^{-1} : 3037 (C-H str., ArH), 1555 (C=N str.), 1772 (C=O str.), 1368 (N-O str.), 1091 (C-O str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 7.59-7.17 (18H, m, ArH), 3.78 (2H, t, NCH_2), 4.69 (2H, t, OCH_2), 4.41 (2H, s, SCH_2); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 33.30, 34.44, 36.64, 127.50, 127.63, 127.79, 128.17, 128.25, 129.51, 129.66, 130.10, 130.25, 130.46, 131.08, 131.46, 132.16, 132.42, 135.14, 145.84, 149.52, 159.76, 160.54, 160.70, 168.85, 171.40; MS : m/z : 728 $[\text{M}]^+$.

Antibacterial activity :

Six synthesized compounds were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against pure culture of four pathogenic strains namely *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Klebsilla pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Nutrient agar medium was used for their culture. These were inoculated with suspension of organisms by spread plate method. With the help of sterile borer required numbers of wells were made in the medium and filled with 500 ppm DMF solution of synthesized compounds. After sealing the Petri-dishes with paraffin wax, these were incubated at 37 °C. After 24 h the Petri-dishes were examined for the study of zone of inhibition. The control (standard) drug used was Ciprofloxacin.

The compounds have shown moderate to weaker activity. The activity was found to be significant against *E. coli*, where activity index ranges between 0.60-0.85. Compounds have shown poor activity against *P. aeruginosa*, where activity index average was 0.50 approximately. In this study *B. subtilis* and *K. pneumoniae* shown moderate activity (activity index between 0.46-0.72). It is visualized from the study that ethoxyphthalimide moiety has an enhancing contribution to activity as **5c** has poor activity than **6c**. Substituent effect is also obvious in the table as chloro derivatives have better activity than those without chloro substituent.

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